

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SINGH****FIRST NAME: EVELINA****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2013 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA- 401D

1. What is NOT a rule of thumb for writing?

- Before getting into an evaluation, give a comprehensive description of the assessed theory.¹**
- State the main thesis of the study at or near the beginning of the paper.
- Use evidence when attributing views to the person whose ideas you are.
- Take the views you are discussing seriously.

2. What is the first step in learning the skill of sound research?

- Understand how experienced researchers think about their aims.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenwreck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 13.

² Kate Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*,

- Evaluating sources for relevance and reliability.
- Understand the research topic, problem and working hypothesis.
- Planning a first draft.

3. Mary is doing marketing research for her company which produces cleaning products. She wants to compare three variables (number of products, sales and market percentage) at multiple data points. Which form of graphic representation would best represent the data Mary collected?

Bubble chart.³

- Bar chart.
- Histogram.
- Pie chart.

4. John is testing the hypothesis that there has been an increase in crime in his community since the closing down of the copper plant. Which source is best suited to obtain the statistics for the crime rate in the community?

Primary sources.⁴

- Secondary sources.

Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Ninth edition. (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 20-21.

³ Kate Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 105.

⁴ Kate Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 36.

- Tertiary sources.
- Books from reputable universities.

5. Jack is writing a technical paper on geographical formations in the Paleolithic period.

Which type of bibliography is best suited for this paper?

- Annotated bibliography.**⁵
- Selected bibliography.
- Single-entry bibliography.
- Author-date style.

6. Mary wants to investigate alcohol abuse and domestic violence in her community.

Which qualitative research methodology is best suited to employ to execute this study?

- Case study.**⁶
- Phenomenology.
- Action research.
- Ethnography.

7. David plans to investigate cyberbullying and online social groups. Which qualitative research methodology is best suited to employ to execute this study?

⁵ Kate Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 155.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018), 159-63.

Ethnography.⁷

Case study.

Phenomenology.

Action research.

8. John plans to investigate long-term traumas by family members who lost a family member due to COVID-19. Which qualitative research methodology is best suited to employ to execute this study?

Phenomenology.⁸

Action research.

Ethnography.

Case study.

9. A college professor facilitating a graduate course in Research Methods, Jane wants to investigate the advantages of enabling the course asynchronously. Which qualitative research methodology is best suited to employ to execute this study?

Action research.⁹

Case study.

Phenomenology.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition, 164-67.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition, 168-70.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition, 179-82.

Ethnography.

10. According to the European Commission manual, which is an acceptable way of citing judgments?

Judgment of the Court of Justice of 12 July 2005, *Schempp*, C-403/03, ECLI:EU:C:2005:446, paragraphs 22 to 24.¹⁰

Judgment of the Court of Justice of 12 July 2005, *Schempp*, C-403/03, ECLI: EU: C: 2005: 446, paragraphs 22 to 24.

Judgment of the Court of Justice (12 July 2005), *Schempp*, C-403/03, ECLI:EU:C:2005:446, paragraphs 22 to 24.

Judgment of the Court of Justice of 12 July 2005, *Schempp*, C-403/03, ECLI:EU:C:2005:446, para. 22 to 24.

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Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018.

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European Commission. *English Style Guide*. 8th rev. ed. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth*

¹⁰ European Commission. *English Style Guide*. 8th rev. ed. (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2021), 89-90.

Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Ninth edition. Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.